

**Nutritional and Economic Value of Relevant Fish and Shellfish in Bangladesh:
Insights into Diet Quality and Regional Food System Policies in South Asia**

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Abstract

Fish plays a pivotal role in the diets, nutrition, and economies of Bangladesh and the broader South Asian region, serving as an affordable primary source of animal protein and a livelihood for millions of rural households. However, comprehensive nutrient profiles at the local scale in countries like Bangladesh remain limited. To address this gap, the study examined the proximate compositions (biochemical properties) of four commercially important fish species (*Oreochromis niloticus*, *Labeo bata*, *Pangasius hypophthalmus*, and *Harpodon nehereus*) and one crustacean species (*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*) of two different sizes, collected from a local fish market. Proximate compositions, including moisture, crude protein, crude lipid, ash, and carbohydrate were analyzed in the fish/shellfish muscles using established methods while maintaining standard quality control and assurance measures. Additionally, a five-week survey of local market data was conducted to assess protein-to-price ratios. Results revealed a wide range of values across species: moisture (65.48–86.14%), crude protein (12.07–20.77%), lipid (0.31–5.69%), ash (0.77–1.93%), and carbohydrate (0.56–7.93%). The market analysis indicated that small-sized tilapia offers a higher protein-to-price ratio compared with other species. These findings demonstrate the nutritional and economic value of locally available fish and shellfish, supporting their integration into national sustainable nutrition strategies and food security initiatives. The results also provide guidance for informed decisions on fish production, trade, and consumption to enhance nutrition and livelihoods in Bangladesh and across South Asia.

Keywords: Proximate compositions, Fish/shellfish, Diet quality, Economic value, Food policy